

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D2.1: Dissemination and communication plan

AUTHORS:

Krzysztof JAJUGA (*Uniwersytet Ekonomiczny we Wrocławiu*)

Renata GWOŹDZIEWICZ-PĘCHERZEWSKA (*Uniwersytet Ekonomiczny we Wrocławiu*)

APPROVED IN 2018 BY:

Jan ANNAERT (*Universiteit Antwerpen*)

Wolfgang KÖNIG (*Goethe-Universität Frankfurt*)

Angelo RIVA (*École d'Économie de Paris*)

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I. Website – creation by WordPress engine

1. WP2 creates website layout and implements basic information about the project.
2. WP1 is the only one that provides key and reliable information. The information provided by WP1 guarantees the highest standards for image of the EURHISFIRM project. WP1 is the credible source of all key project related information and actions.
3. WP2 is obliged to base only on information sourced by WP1 and its strategic and operational project management. That means only information received from WP1 or approved by WP1 will be placed on website during project duration.

II. Social media

1. WP2 creates profiles on social media proposed by WP1.
2. Information on profiles will be synchronized with the website, and the meaning will be the same as on the website.
3. WP2 follows the similar method used for the website (described above, I.3) to post information on the social media profiles. WP1 is the only one that provides key and reliable information. The information provided by WP1 guarantees the highest standards for image of the EURHISFIRM project. WP1 is credible source of all key project related information and actions.
4. WP2 is obliged to base only on information sourced by WP1 and its strategic and operational project management. That means only information received from WP1 or approved by WP1 will be placed on social media profiles during project duration.
5. WP2 pastes information after receiving it directly from WP1.
6. All other participants' suggestions according to implement any information should be sent to WP1 first.

III. Media release/press release

1. WP2 prepares template for media release distribution.
2. Frequency of media release distribution depends on possible content suggested by WP1 – suggested twice a year.

KEY POINTS/STEPS

1. Each country creates its own “media contact database”. Timetable of preparation could be parallel with stakeholders’ distribution list – M8.
2. WP2 receives information from WP1, and for 2 weeks prepares template with content ready to be sent to media.
3. WP2 forwards the prepared press release to each Project Partner.
4. Each partner should consider translation of the press release into its language.
5. To complete the “media contact database”, WP3 could support each Project Partner in meeting the legislation requirements according to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

IV. Distribution Network

1. WP1 supports Project Partners in case of any doubts, regarding who from stakeholders should be added to the networking distribution list (distribution database).
2. To unify the range of information, each Project Partner (i.e. each country) develops a database of its stakeholders (distribution database) using the following format: name of the institution, contact person, e-mail address, postal address, telephone number.
3. The distribution database consists of the following group of entities:
 - ▶▶ Policy: representatives of central banks, regulatory bodies, policy makers;
 - ▶▶ Academic: representatives of universities, research institutions, libraries, archives, RIs, and other academic data platforms;
 - ▶▶ Business: representatives from financial institutions, stock exchanges, data vendors, and business associations;
 - ▶▶ Society: representatives of think tanks, consumers’ associations and the general public.

4. This range of information will be used for the surveys elaborated by WP5, WP8 and WP10 representing opportunities for communication activities. WP5, WP8, WP10 are therefore asked to send to WP1 until M4 their needs in the field of components of distribution database (if they need more than proposed format of it). WP1 informs directly all Project Partners about requirements of distribution database until M5 to follow up its correct format.
5. Timetable for distribution database to be prepared – duration M6.
6. Each Partner takes care of the specific security of its distribution database of stakeholders, its compliance with legal requirements and the correctness of approvals in the scope of the GDPR. In case of any doubts in the field of data security, it transmits questions to WP3.
7. Ready lists (distribution database) held by each of the Project Partners will serve as a mailing list to distribute mailings.

V. Webinars, podcast/videos, newsletters

1. Quarterly, semi-annually or annually. Frequency depends on the WP1 tips that will be provided on a regular basis.
2. WP1 stands as the only source of all key project related information and actions. It provides key messages to communicate and reliable information.
3. WP2 will support in accordance with the requirements of a specific action in the preparation of the technical side of the undertaking.
4. WP2 will take care of placing links on website to each of actions like webinars, podcasts, and videos.
5. WP2 in coordination with WP1 will prepare and send prepared newsletters in English, intended for further distribution or as a basis for translation into different languages and then distribution by each of the partners to their distribution database.
6. WP1 supports WP2 with key information distributed in the newsletter.

KEY POINT

- ▶ Time to prepare each webinar/podcast/video depends on the selected channel, approx. 1 working month.

VI. Appendix: Communication plan timelines

Creation: Website, social media, and media release/Press release

YEAR 1

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
	www		Social Media			Media release/ press release						
CREATION	<p>Developing the appearance of the page, subpages - graphic design of the site. This stage is responsible for the preparation based on the concept outlined in the design of the website, navigation system, typography and planned colour elements related to increasing the conversion on the pages. At this stage, we consider elements related to the future optimisation of page loading time.</p> <p>POINTS/STEPS WP2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Range of colours • Graphic concept/graphic design • Navigation (menu) • CMS 		<p>Create profiles. The profiles are synchronized with the website. The message is the same as on the website's news pages.</p> <p>POINTS/STEPS WP2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook • LinkedIn • Twitter 			<p>Each country/Project Partner prepares its own list of media to be sent for press releases. List to be ready by M8. WP2 prepares in template the prepared press release. Each country translates if there is need to other languages.</p> <p>POINTS/STEPS WP2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template • Preparation for Press Release • Distribute to Project Partners to be forwarded to chosen media 						
	<p>www</p> <p>Concept sent to WP1 - comments and / or approval</p>		<p>Social Media</p> <p>Project sent to WP1 - comments and / or approval</p>									

Day by day objectives and activities: Website, social media, and media release/press release

YEAR 1 *

DAY BY DAY OBJECTIVES AND ACTIVITIES

* These activities are continued in a similar manner in Year 2 and Year 3 (with an end-of-project conference to be held in Year 3)

Creation: Project identity and brand

YEAR 1

